

Isolation and Identification of *Salmonella* from Faecal Droppings of Pigeon in Some Locations of Kware Local Government

*¹Bello H. A. and ²Umar A.

¹Department of Microbiology, Sokoto State University

²Department of Biological Sciences, Sokoto State University

*Correspondence: aishaumar258@gmail.com

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Abstract

The main habitats and carriers of *Salmonella* species are mostly humans, plants and other animals. They are often spread by birds, reptiles, insects, through food stuff, soil and fecal matter. Because of their mobility, birds such as pigeons could be a major transporter of *Salmonella* species. This study is aimed at investigating the prevalence of *Salmonella* species in pigeons found in selected locations in Kware Local Government area of Sokoto state. Twenty-five samples from five different locations (5 droppings per location) were obtained and used to investigate the prevalence of *salmonella* in the area through isolation and identification. This was carried out using macroscopic and microscopic evaluation. The results showed the presence of opaque, translucent, colorless, smooth round, colonies. The biochemical characterization of the bacterial isolates showed that sixteen samples (64%) from the total isolates tested positive for the following tests; indole, citrate utilization, hydrogen sulfite production, sugar production, urease and motility. Four out of the five isolates from the first location showed the presence of salmonella (i.e.16% of the total); four tested positive from the second location (16%); three from the third location (12%); three from the fourth location (12%) and two from the fifth location (8%). The findings provide evidence that some pigeon birds in the area are colonized by pathogenic *Salmonella* that could be harboring multidrug resistant genes. There is need to develop strategies to urgently curtail the spread of these harmful pathogens.

Keywords: Faecal droppings, Isolation, Kware Local Government, Pigeon, and *Salmonella*

1.0 Introduction

Salmonella are facultative intracellular Gram-negative bacteria that belong to the family enterobacteriaceae. They are typically found in humans, domestic and some wild animals including birds [1]. The main habitat of most *Salmonella* species is the intestinal tract of humans and other animals. It is also found in the intestinal tract of birds, reptiles and sometime in insects, soil and fecal matter [1]. Many animals, especially cattle, chickens, rodents, reptiles and amphibians may harbor the organisms in their intestines and show no signs of illness, and most infected humans get salmonellosis from handling these animals [2].

Salmonella infection is a major public health problem in many developing countries due to the

bacterial large and varied animal reservoir. This bacterium may survive in humid soil, faeces and water for months and may cause new infections in both human and birds [1]. *Salmonella* infection most often causes gastroenteritis, which can range from mild to severe [3]. They can cause gastroenteritis, which is often uncomplicated and does not need treatment but could be severe in the young and elderly [2]. The presence of this bacterium in the intestinal tract of human and domestic animal can create a cycle of chronic carriers of human and domestic birds [3]. As the bacteria colonizes the intestinal tract, the organisms are excreted in faeces from which they may be transmitted to a large number of places notably water and food; When such polluted water or food is consumed by an individual, he may get infected and shed the organism through fecal

matter, thus continuing the cycle of contamination [4]. The effect of infection with *Salmonella* is determined by the condition of the host and the status of the bacterium. While age, genetic and environmental factors mostly determine the condition of the host [5], the status of the bacterium is determined by so-called virulence factors [6]. A review revealed that the prevalence of multidrug resistance is on the rise in African and this may pose difficulty in the treatment of human *Salmonella* infections [1]. Few African countries have adequate information on *Salmonella* [6]. This includes Nigeria, where the few studies conducted so far show different difficulties, such as the limited number of samples considered, the lack of representativeness of the samples selected, the lack of access, and the restricted geographical coverage [6].

Many research conducted have shown the possibility that domestic birds can act as spreaders of antibiotic-resistant bacteria. There are also examples where domestic bird migration has been related to the spread of pathogens, such as the spreading of West Nile Virus in the US [1]. Similarly, [7] isolated antibiotic-resistant *Salmonella* strains from black-headed gulls which suggested that the bacterium was spread through migration. Antibiotic resistant strains including ESBL-producing *E. coli* have also been isolated from birds from remote and preservation areas [8]. This could be interpreted as a possible tract of human activity, but at least in some cases, it seems more reasonable with the spread through bird migration [1].

In Kware Local Government area of Sokoto State, domesticated birds (pigeon and turkey) are reared freely in and around the homes and their fecal droppings can easily contaminate food and the environment. Some of these pathogens may be recent pathogens and may not have been detected before while some might even have become resistant to drugs commonly used to treat the diseases they cause. Resistance to antibacterial agents has been on the rise with regards to major bacterial pathogens [9]. Several clones of multidrug resistant *Salmonella* have been detected and their prevalence has expanded worldwide [9]. The Center for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC] in the US estimates that there are about 1.35 million cases of Salmonellosis, with 26,500 hospitalizations and 420 deaths annually in the US [5]. This figure is likely to be higher in developing countries (such as Nigeria). There has

been a reported case of outbreak of food poisoning as a result of *Salmonella* in Nigeria that has led to deaths and hospitalizations [4]. Akinyemi et al., [3] reported that 21 out of the 36 States in Nigeria have reported *Salmonella*-associated diseases. The spread covered all the geographical zones of the country. Considering the severity of diseases caused by salmonella there is a need to investigate its prevalence in this part of the world where reliable records is scanty [3, 10].

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Collection of fecal droppings of domesticated pigeon

2.1 Study Area

Kware Local Government Area is a semi urban-town and an area council headquarters, in Sokoto State of Nigeria Kware is located between latitudes $13^{\circ} 00''$ to $13^{\circ} 20' 0''$ N and longitudes $5^{\circ} 10' 0''$ to $5^{\circ} 30' 0''$ E with an area of 554 km^2 [11].

2.2 Sample Collection

The households where pigeons were reared in the area were first identified. Five different locations were randomly chosen for the study. Sample of fecal droppings of pigeons were collected from the five households, from five different locations in the local government area. A total of 25 fecal droppings sample were collected in sterile airtight container and transported to the Microbiology Laboratory of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, for analysis.

2.3 Media Preparation

The media used in this research were Nutrient Agar [NA], Salmonella-Shigella Agar [SSA], Simon's Citrate Agar [SCA], Xylose lysine deoxycholate Agar [XLD], Urea Agar and Triple Sugar Iron Agar [TSI]. All media were prepared according to the manufacturer's instruction and checked for sterility before use.

2.4 Isolation of bacteria

Bacteria were isolated according to the procedure described by [6]. Ten grams (10 g) of each fecal sample was weighed and transferred to 100 ml of Selenite broth in 200 ml conical flasks and incubated over night at 37°C . One ml of the pre-

enriched sample was transferred aseptically into 9 ml of buffered peptone water, and was incubated at 37 °C for 24 hrs. A loopfull of the buffered peptone water mixture was sub-cultured onto xylose lysine deoxycholate (XLD) agar, and Salmonella–Shigella agar, using spread plate method. All inoculated plates were incubated aerobically at 37 °C for 24 h. After 24 hrs, the plate was examined for typical *Salmonella* colonies growth characteristics. *Salmonella* colonies grown on XLD changes the medium colour from red to yellow and colonies appear with a black center, while on SSA the colonies appear colorless with black center [11]. The suspected colonies were sub cultured on Nutrient Agar to obtain the pure isolates.

2.5 Identification and characterization of isolates

Identification of bacterial isolates was done based on the morphology (Gram staining) and biochemical characterization according to the methods described by [12, 13].

2.5.1 Gram's Staining

Thin smear of the suspected *Salmonella* pure colony was made on a grease free slide and fixed under burning flame. A crystal violet solution was then applied to cover the smear for 30 seconds and washed using distilled water. Secondly, lugol's iodine was added to the surface for 30 seconds. 1ml to 2mls of Acetone was poured over the smear to decolorize the stain, and lastly, Safranin was applied for two minute, which was washed and allows viewing under oil immersion lens. Presence of purple cells indicated Gram-Positive bacteria and reddish pink cells indicated Gram-Negative [12, 13].

2.5.2 Biochemical Tests

Biochemical tests were carried out using standard methods [13] as follows:

2.5.3 Indole Test

One percent (%) tryptophan broth in a test tube was inoculated with bacterial colony. After incubation period of 37 °C for 48 hours, then one millilitre (1 ml) of chloroform was added to the broth. The test tube was shaken gently, then 2.0 ml of Kovac's reagent was added and this was shaken gently and allowed to stand for twenty minutes. After which tubes were observed for the

formation of red colouration at the top layer indicating positive result [13].

2.5.4 Citrate Utilization Test

The inoculum was picked from the center of a well isolated colony and streaking the slant back and forth in a test tube containing Simmon's citrate medium and this was incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C. Tubes were observed for the development of deep-blue colouration after 48hrs incubation [12].

2.5.5 Methyl Red-Voges-Proskauer [MR-VP] Test

Five milliliters (5 ml) of MRVP broth was inoculated with the test organism with a syringe and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C. After which, one milliliter (1 ml) of the broth was transferred into a small test tube. Three drops (3 drops) of methyl red was added to the tubes and shaken gently. A red colour on the addition of the methyl red indicator signified a positive test while yellow colour signified a negative test. To the rest of the broth in the original tube, five (5) drops of 4 % potassium hydroxide (KOH) was added, followed by fifteen (15) drops of 5% α -naphthol in ethanol. The test tube [sealed with cotton plug] was shaken and placed in a sloping position. The development of a red colour starting from the liquid-air interface within 1 hour indicated a VP positive test while no colour change indicated a VP negative test [12].

2.5.6 Sugar Fermentation and gas Production Test

This was carried out according to the procedure described by Oyeleke and Manga [12]. A little growth of each isolate was inoculated by streaking and stabbing with a straight wire into triple sugar iron agar medium and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. After the incubation period, the tubes was examined for fermentation of any of the sugars in the medium indicated by change in colour from red to yellow and formation of a crack or raise in location of the medium, indicating a positive test [12].

2.5.7 Hydrogen Sulphide Production

The isolate was inoculated using straight wire loop onto prepared TSI medium, then incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours and observed for the Presence of black coloration indicating positive test [12].

2.5.8 Motility Test

The isolates were inoculated using straight wire loop onto prepared sulphate indole motility [SIM] medium then incubated at 37 °C for 24 hrs. This was observed for diffused zone of growth flaring out from the line of inoculation [12].

2.5.9 Urease Test

The test organism was inoculated into urea broth and incubated at 37 °C for 48 hours. At the end of which, tubes were observed for the presence of purple pink colour indicating positive test [12].

3.0 Result

Table 1 shows the results of the macroscopy and microscopy of the bacterial isolates obtained from pigeon bird feces collected from the study sites deoxycholate citrate agar (DCA). Sixteen out of the twenty four isolates display a colorless,

smooth, shiny, and translucent surface along with black center colonies and Gram-negative, rod-shaped bacteria under the microscope.

The result of biochemical characterization of the bacterial isolates from fecal droppings of pigeon birds is shown in Table 2. Twenty Four Samples from the total isolates tested positive for indole, VP, citrate utilization, hydrogen sulfite production, sugar production, urease and motility test, which was identified as *Salmonella* species.

The fecal droppings of pigeons from the selected locations, that tested positive for *Salmonella*, has a total percentage frequency of occurrence of 64 % as shown in Table 1. Four out of the five isolates (16 %), from the first location showed the presence of *salmonellas*, four (16%) tested positive from the second location; three (12 %), from the third location, three (12 %) from the fourth location, and two (8 %) from the fifth location.

Table 1: Percentage frequency and morphology of *salmonella* isolates from the different locations in Kware local government

Locations	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Characteristics
Location 1	4	16.0	Opaque, translucent, colourless, smooth round colonies
Location 2	4	16.0	Opaque, translucent, colourless, smooth round colonies
Location 3	3	12.0	Opaque, translucent, colourless, smooth round colonies
Location 4	3	12.0	Opaque, translucent, colourless, smooth round colonies
Location 5	2	8.9	Opaque, translucent, colourless, smooth round colonies
Total	16	64	Opaque, translucent, colourless, smooth round colonies

Table 2: Biochemical test of isolates from different location in Kware Local Government

Samples	Biochemical Test									Confirmed isolates
	Gram Reaction	Morphology	Indole	Citrate Utilization	MR-VP	Sugar Production	H ₂ S	Motility	Urease	
LOC 1	-Ve	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species
LOC 2	-Ve	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species
LOC 3	-Ve	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species
LOC 4	-Ve	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species
LOC 5	-Ve	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species
LOC 6	-Ve	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species
LOC 7	-Ve	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species
LOC 8	-Ve	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species
LOC 9	-Ve	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species
LOC 10	-Ve	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species
LOC 11	-Ve	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species
LOC 12	-Ve	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species
LOC 13	-Ve	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species
LOC 14	-	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species
LOC 15	-Ve	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species
Loc 16	-Ve	Rod	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Salmonella</i> species

4.0 Discussion

In the present Study, *Salmonella* were isolated from fecal droppings of pigeon birds in some locations of Kware local government area of Sokoto State. The morphological test showed that all the isolated bacteria have the same

characteristics. Sixteen out of the twenty four isolates display a colorless, smooth, shiny, and translucent surface along with black center colonies and Gram-negative, rod-shaped bacteria under the microscope. These are all characteristics of *salmonella* bacteria [12].

Of the 25 samples tested for *Salmonella*, 16 (64.0%) samples tested. In Gram-staining, the morphological characteristic of the isolated *Salmonella* species exhibited Gram negative, small rod, singular paired arrangement under a microscope which was in line with the work of [14, 15]. All the isolates were indole, and voges proskauer negative because almost all the Serotypes of *Salmonella* do not produce indole, hydrolyze urea positive using biochemical characterization and deaminate phenylalanine or tryptophan [16]. While all the isolates were found to be motile, utilized citrate, Fermented sugars, produce hydrogen sulfide, methyl red, and urease positive. The implication of this high percentage is that pigeon birds can be a major source of the spread of salmonella in the area. As they are not restricted to boundaries the possibility of contact with their fecal droppings is there. They are also consumed as meat in the area which may also serve as a channel for the spread of the harmful bacteria.

5.0 Conclusion

This study has investigated the prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. from fecal droppings of pigeons in some selected locations of Kware Local Government Area of Sokoto State. The study showed that as high as 60 % of the samples considered are carriers of *salmonella*. The high value obtained is an indication of the high risk faced by the people of the area to contacting the harmful bacteria. This should be a matter of great concern to the government and the people of the area. From the public health point of consideration this source can accidentally serve as a potential vehicle for transmission of *Salmonella* spp. to other animals and human beings. The study only identified the prevalence of salmonella, so, further studies need to be conducted to identify the types of salmonella and their susceptibility to drugs. Urgent action need to be taken to curtail further spread of the bacteria to mitigate against future outbreak of epidemic coursed by salmonella in the area.

6.0 Recommendations

Base on the results and conclusions drawn from this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. There is need to extend this study to other parts of the region to provide information on the prevalence of *salmonella* in the region.
2. The health authority needs to educate the people of the area on the need to take measures to reduce the spread of the deadly gens in the area.
3. The type of *salmonella* present in the area needs to be identified through molecular study.
4. The susceptibility of the pathogens to currently available drugs needs to be determined.

7.0 Acknowledgement

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8.0 Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

9.0 Reference

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